

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIALS AND DATA

Towards harmonization of metal analysis in plastics: comparison of acid digestion protocols in conventional and compostable plastics

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Table S1 Metal concentrations of ERM[®]-EC681m determined after microwave-assisted acid digestion followed by ICP-MS analysis. Data are separated by protocol applied (1+H, 2+H, 3+H, 1, 2 and 3) as outlined in paragraph 2.2. Average values and standard deviations of six replicates analyses ($n = 6$) per sample are reported, together with recoveries.

Metals	ERM [®] -E681m Certified value		1+H		2+H		3+H	
	[mg kg ⁻¹]	[mg kg ⁻¹]	Recovery [%]	[mg kg ⁻¹]	Recovery [%]	[mg kg ⁻¹]	Recovery [%]	
As	17.0 ± 1.2	17.0 ± 1.0	100.0 ± 5.9	15.8 ± 1.0	92.9 ± 5.9	14.9 ± 0.5	87.6 ± 2.9	
Cd	146 ± 5	146 ± 3	100.0 ± 2.1	146 ± 10	100.0 ± 6.8	149 ± 6	102.1 ± 4.1	
Cr	45.1 ± 1.9	44.5 ± 1.4	98.7 ± 3.1	45.0 ± 3.4	99.8 ± 7.5	45.6 ± 1.7	101.1 ± 3.8	
Pb	69.7 ± 2.5	69.8 ± 0.9	100.1 ± 1.3	69.4 ± 4.6	99.6 ± 6.6	71.8 ± 2.7	103.0 ± 3.9	
Sb	86 ± 7	87 ± 2	101.2 ± 2.3	84 ± 6	97.7 ± 7.0	61 ± 4	70.9 ± 4.7	
Sn	99 ± 6	99 ± 3	100.0 ± 3.0	105 ± 6	106.1 ± 6.1	30 ± 4	30.3 ± 4.0	
Zn	1170 ± 40	1169 ± 27	99.9 ± 2.3	1233 ± 82	105.4 ± 7.0	1225 ± 44	104.7 ± 3.8	

Metals	ERM [®] -E681m Certified value		1		2		3	
	[mg kg ⁻¹]	[mg kg ⁻¹]	Recovery [%]	[mg kg ⁻¹]	Recovery [%]	[mg kg ⁻¹]	Recovery [%]	
As	17.0 ± 1.2	14.0 ± 0.7	82.4 ± 4.1	14.3 ± 0.5	84.1 ± 2.9	13.1 ± 0.5	77.1 ± 2.9	
Cd	146 ± 5	130 ± 5	89.0 ± 3.4	137 ± 3	93.8 ± 2.1	136 ± 5	93.2 ± 3.4	
Cr	45.1 ± 1.9	42.5 ± 1.9	94.2 ± 4.2	42.6 ± 1.2	94.6 ± 2.7	42.6 ± 1.6	94.5 ± 3.5	
Pb	69.7 ± 2.5	60.4 ± 2.6	86.7 ± 3.7	65.1 ± 3.0	93.4 ± 4.3	67.1 ± 3.8	96.3 ± 5.5	
Sb	86 ± 7	71 ± 3	82.6 ± 3.5	75 ± 2	87.2 ± 2.3	54 ± 3	62.8 ± 3.5	
Sn	99 ± 6	95 ± 4	96.0 ± 4.0	100 ± 2	101.0 ± 2.0	24 ± 3	24.2 ± 3.0	
Zn	1170 ± 40	978 ± 38	83.6 ± 3.2	1036 ± 19	88.5 ± 1.6	1009 ± 39	86.2 ± 3.3	

Table S2 Metal concentrations of end-use LDPE and compostable plastic bags No. 1 and 2 determined after microwave-assisted acid digestion followed by ICP-MS analysis. Data are separated by protocol applied (1+H, 2+H, 3+H, 1, 2 and 3) as outlined in paragraph 2.2. Table values display averages and standard deviations of six replicates analyses ($n = 6$) per sample.

LDPE bag	1+H	2+H	3+H
Metals	[mg kg ⁻¹]	[mg kg ⁻¹]	[mg kg ⁻¹]
As	0.38 ± 0.02	0.29 ± 0.05	0.28 ± 0.01
Cd	0.100 ± 0.003	0.104 ± 0.003	0.110 ± 0.006
Cr	0.930 ± 0.065	0.957 ± 0.186	0.994 ± 0.063
Pb	0.54 ± 0.06	0.49 ± 0.08	0.50 ± 0.03
Sb	22.5 ± 0.2	11.3 ± 7.3	1.8 ± 1.1
Sn	0.66 ± 0.04	0.65 ± 0.08	0.32 ± 0.05
Zn	149.0 ± 1.6	158.2 ± 5.1	190.8 ± 5.8
Ti	3113.4 ± 1152.5	164.3 ± 78.6	42.3 ± 12.2
Compostable bag No.1			
Metals	[mg kg ⁻¹]	[mg kg ⁻¹]	[mg kg ⁻¹]
As	0.17 ± 0.06	0.16 ± 0.02	<MDL
Cd	0.021 ± 0.002	0.018 ± 0.004	0.017 ± 0.002
Cr	1.346 ± 0.006	0.486 ± 0.033	1.769 ± 0.293
Pb	0.468 ± 0.014	0.446 ± 0.042	0.485 ± 0.020
Sb	<MDL	<MDL	<MDL
Sn	4.19 ± 0.15	3.33 ± 0.16	1.34 ± 0.23
Zn	4.2 ± 0.5	2.7 ± 0.5	<MDL
Ti	2408.3 ± 213.5	216.3 ± 8.8	182.9 ± 7.2
Compostable bag No.2			
Metals	[mg kg ⁻¹]	[mg kg ⁻¹]	[mg kg ⁻¹]
As	0.071 ± 0.034	0.070 ± 0.029	<MDL
Cd	0.008 ± 0.006	0.011 ± 0.005	0.010 ± 0.007
Cr	1.23 ± 0.31	0.50 ± 0.33	1.74 ± 0.40
Pb	0.660 ± 0.024	0.716 ± 0.062	0.683 ± 0.056
Sb	<MDL	<MDL	<MDL
Sn	3.0 ± 0.1	3.4 ± 0.4	1.4 ± 0.3
Zn	9.0 ± 3.8	5.9 ± 2.9	2.7 ± 1.8
Ti	1603.1 ± 259.0	193.1 ± 8.7	136 ± 3.5

Table S3 ICP-MS working parameters.

Parameter	Value
RF Power	1550 W
Nebulizer gas flow	1.06 L/min
Auxiliary gas flow	0.80 L/min
Cooling gas flow	13.99 L/min
Dwell time (ms)	300 ms
He flow rate (collision cell)	4.34 mL/min

Table S4 Method detection limits (MDLs) estimated by means of six replicates of method blanks for each protocol (1+H, 2+H, 3+H, 1, 2 and 3). Values are expressed as mg kg⁻¹ based on a 100 mg solid sample.

MDL	1+H	2+H	3+H	1	2	3
Metals	[mg kg ⁻¹] on a 100 mg solid sample	[mg kg ⁻¹] on a 100 mg solid sample	[mg kg ⁻¹] on a 100 mg solid sample	[mg kg ⁻¹] on a 100 mg solid sample	[mg kg ⁻¹] on a 100 mg solid sample	[mg kg ⁻¹] on a 100 mg solid sample
As	0.060	0.017	0.057	0.076	0.021	0.027
Cd	0.002	0.008	0.009	0.001	0.004	0.005
Cr	0.13	0.10	0.23	0.09	0.04	0.12
Pb	0.02	0.03	0.06	0.01	0.01	0.03
Sb	0.096	0.040	0.617	0.122	0.030	0.744
Sn	0.030	0.074	0.066	0.020	0.048	0.021
Zn	0.40	0.94	0.84	0.30	0.98	0.73

Fig. S1 Images of samples considered in the study. ERM[®]-EC681m is displayed in panel a, while end-use LDPE is in panel b and compostable plastic bags No. 1 and 2 are shown in panels c and d, respectively.

Fig. S2 ATR-FTIR data of samples considered in the study. ERM®-EC681m is displayed in panel a, while end-use LDPE is in panel b. Panels c and d report the spectra from compostable plastic bags No. 1 and 2, respectively. A PBAT reference spectrum is displayed in panel e and, lastly, panel f shows the reference spectra of starch.

a) LDPE	$\left[\text{CH}_2 - \text{CH}_2 \right]_n$
b) PBAT	
c) Starch	

Fig. S3 Chemical structures of samples considered in the study. LDPE structure is displayed in panel a. Panels b and c, namely, report the chemical structure of PBAT and starch, the two main components of compostable plastic bags No. 1 and 2.

Fig. S4 SEM-EDX spectra of undissolved fragments after incomplete digestions. Panel a shows an example of a spectrum from end-use LDPE bag digested with protocol 2+H, while panel b displays a spectrum of residuals from the compostable plastic bag No. 1 after application of protocol 3+H.